

Building a Wikibase Instance for African Literary Metadata: First insights

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Abstract

The African Literary Metadata project (ALMEDA) investigates the historical development of library catalogues and archives from the 19th century to the present.¹ It does so in order to understand how cataloguing standards manufactured a conceptual split between written and oral, book and non-book literary cultures on the African continent, a split which devalued oral forms as ethnographic information without literary or aesthetic value. This has had significant consequences for the African literary archive, since metadata – whether for cataloguing or commercial purposes – has favoured formally published and commercially traded books over other literary forms of expression.

Indeed, books do not dominate literary expression on the continent itself, where their exorbitant price and complicated colonial history means that literature thrives in other forms and modes. These include print forms, such as newspapers, low-cost ‘zine’ pamphlet literatures, comic books, self-published novels and literary magazines; oral and performed forms, like spoken word poetry, storytelling and street theatre; and a wide range of digital forms, such as Facebook and blog fictions, Insta-fiction, YouTube fictions, WhatsApp fiction and poetry, and other diverse forms of online poetry.

The ALMEDA project aims to create a multilingual knowledge structure and searchable and editable linked data repository of these often uncatalogued African literary materials and their creators.² Working with multimodal forms, across an immense geographical area and in potentially thousands of languages, is a challenge massively exacerbated by the fact that most of the materials we are interested in cataloguing have no existing structured data presence. This presentation

¹ For more information about ALMEDA, visit the project website: <https://almedaresearch.org/>

² For examples of the material currently gathered, see ALMEDA's data collection on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/almeda>.

focuses on the project's first efforts to address these challenges by building a linked data repository using Wikidata.

To rectify the absence and invisibility of African literary forms on the internet, ALMEDA needs a Linked Open Data repository that is able to handle multilingual data and provides the necessary flexibility to create metadata descriptions of various literary forms generally not captured in bibliographic databases. To this end, the open-source software Wikibase was selected as the basis for ALMEDA's repository.³ Wikibase is the software behind Wikipedia's sister project Wikidata, the free, multilingual collaborative knowledge base (Diefenbach et al. 2021). Wikidata acts as central storage for the structured data of Wikimedia projects and provides support to many other sites and services.⁴ The content of Wikidata can be interlinked to other open datasets on the linked data web (Vrandečić & Krötzsch 2014). Further reasons for choosing Wikibase included its accessibility and ease-of-use, the availability of already-existing relevant properties and records, and compatibility with one of the aims of ALMEDA to open up for data entry by community members and collaborators.

Despite Wikidata's reach – it currently contains 114 million objects and links to more than 9000 external datasets – ALMEDA decided not to enter its metadata directly to Wikidata, but to set up a private Wikibase instance, running on the university server.⁵ This decision was taken in order to maintain control over and ensure the quality of the project's data. Whereas Wikidata is completely public and can be edited by anyone, a Wikibase instance is a private version of the software where the owner can determine its configuration and use. Working within Wikidata would have obliged ALMEDA to adhere to Wikidata's standards and community decisions. Furthermore, the project wanted to avoid potential clashes with Wikidata's notability criteria demanding entities to be verifiable with serious and publicly available references such as university-level textbooks reference books, academic journals, or newspapers. These references do not (yet) exist for the vast majority of the primary data ALMEDA researchers collect on African literatures. The project

³ <https://wikiba.se/>

⁴ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

⁵ Projects without the necessary resources to set up and maintain a Wikibase application on a server can create an instance on Wikibase cloud, a service hosted by Wikimedia Germany for free. Projects could also consider joining FactGrid. This research platform, based on Wikibase software and maintained by Thuringian State and University Library, currently hosts about 50 research projects.

covers informal and ephemeral literatures that are absent in global bibliographic databases and library catalogues and therefore lack external identifiers which could be used to verify bibliographic references in Wikidata such as the International Standard Book Number (ISBN), Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Online Computer Library Center (OCLC) control number and work identifier, or other external identifiers issued by a (national) library.

A newly created Wikibase instance has no predefined properties (i.e. fields) with which to enter data, and no value lists to choose from: this has to be built up from scratch. As starting point, then, for populating the instance, existing properties and items available on Wikidata were collected. This included data on countries and historical countries, cities, languages, occupations, literary genres as well as people with literary professions, publishing companies, awards, and festivals. SPARQL queries were used to extract this data, aiming to gather all potentially relevant items while at the same time ensuring compatibility with the project's metadata model. The lack of existing data and varying quality made this process challenging. The retrieved records were unevenly distributed across the African countries, with countries such as South Africa, Egypt, and Nigeria making up the largest bulk of retrieved records, while no or only a few records were retrieved for countries like Seychelles, South Sudan, and Eswatini. The limited data, furthermore, varied in quality, in terms of accurate use of properties, the number of statements, and links to external identifiers and knowledge bases. Before adding the retrieved data to the Wikibase instance, the data was manually reviewed for completeness, accuracy and relevance. Any items with incorrect statements were removed. Any remaining inconsistencies were addressed during the upload process using the open-source tool OpenRefine.⁶

With the foundation of the ALMEDA instance put into place, the next steps of the project focus on expanding, enriching, verifying, and editing the data on the instance through case studies by researchers, materials gathered from digitized newspapers and magazines, secondary sources such as websites and scholarly literature, and donations from collaborating partners, such as the poetry festival Poetry Africa (van Loenen et al. 2025).⁷ Furthermore, the project aims to create a user-

⁶ <https://openrefine.org/>

⁷ <https://poetryafrica.ukzn.ac.za/>

friendly interface for searching the database, enable data entry through Cradle⁸, a form-based tool, and to realize bidirectional federated queries between the ALMEDA instance and Wikidata.⁹

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⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Cradle>

⁹ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/Federated_queries